

O'QUVCHILARGA PYTHON TILIDA REKURSIV DASTURLASHNI O'RGATISH VA UNING SAMARALI USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Keltirilgan ushbu maqolada o'quvchilarga dasturlashni o'rgatish usullari, python dasturlashning afzalliklari, uning qo'llanilishi, darsliklardagi dasturlashlarning amaliyotga tadbiiq qilinishlari va shu bilan birgalikda o'quvchilar bilan ishlashdagi turli xil metodikalar, komputer savodxonligini oshirishdagi qo'llaniladigan texnologiyalar haqida so'z yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Dastur, tizim, malaka, uslublar, dasturlash tili, python, texnika, metodika, analiz.

Annotation: This article discusses methods of teaching programming to students, the advantages of python programming, its application, the application of programming in the textbook, as well as various methods of working with students, technologies used to improve computer literacy.

Key words: Program, system, skills, methods, programming language, python, technique, methodology, analysis.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev tomonidan 2019 yil yanvar oyida ilgari surilgan beshta muhim tashabbusidan uchinchi tashabbusida aholi va yoshlar o'rtasida kompyuter texnologiyalari va internetdan samarali foydalanish chora – tadbirlariga oid dasturi doirasida 2019 – 2020 yillarda tuman va shaharlarda raqamli texnologiyalar o'quv markazi tashkil etish va ularda bepul ta'lim berish, 19 mingga yaqin ijtimoiy soha ob'ektini yuqori tezlikdagi internet tarmog'iga ulash ko'zda tutilmoqda. Hozirgi jadal rivojlanish va turli jarayonlarni avtomatlashtirish hamda robotlashtirish davrida dasturlashni bilish va uni o'z ish jarayonida ishlata olish texnik va pedagogik yo'nalishda ta'lim olayotgan o'quvchi-talabalar uchun juda muhim deb hisoblanadi. Bu zamonaviy mutahassislar uchun eng zaruriy talablardan biridir. Sababi hozirgi kunda informatika turli-tuman sohalarda muvaffaqiyatli ravishda qo'llanilishi mumkinligini hech kim ham rad eta olmaydi. Bugungi maqolamizda ham aynan dasturlashning python tilida dasturlashni o'quvchilarga qiziqarli tarzda tushuntirish, ularning bilimni mustahkamlash haqida so'z yuritiladi. Demak biz avvalo python dasturi o'zi nima, uning ahamiyati qanday, undagi o'rganish mumkin bo'lgan o'ziga xosliklarini bilib olamiz.

Python dasturlash tili samarador yuqori darajadagi ma'lumotlar tuzilmasini

hamda oddiy, ammo samarador bo'lgan ob'yektga yo'naltirilgan dasturlash uslublarini taqdim etadi. Undan tashqari, bu til o'rganish uchun oson va shu bilan birga imkoniyatlari yuqori bo'lgan oz sonli dasturlash tillari jumlasiga kiradi va shu bilan birgalikda unda dasturlash jarayoni juda ham oddiy amalga oshiriladi. Python dasturlash tilining rasmiy sayti - www.python.org bo'lib, uning muallifi Niderlandiyadagi Matematika va informatika ilmiy adqiqot institutida ishlagan Gvido van Rossum deb hisoblanadi. Pythonning o'ziga xosligi esa uning oddiyligi, o'rganishga osonligi, sodda sintaksisga egaligi va dasturlash jarayonini boshlash uchun qulay, erkin va ochiq kodlik dasturiy ta'minotga egaligidir. Undan tashqari, o'z dasturingizni yozish davomida quyi darajadagi detallarni, misol uchun xotirani boshqarishni hisobga olishingizga hech qanday hojat qolmaydi. Bu dasturlash tili ko'plab platformalarda hech qanday o'zgartirishlarsiz ishlay oladi va u interpretatsiya qilinadigan tillar jumlasiga mansub. 4 Bulardan tashqari, Python dasturlash tili imkoniyatlari kengayishga moyil bo'lgan dasturiy til hisoblanadi. Agar siz dasturingizning biror-bir joyini tezroq ishlashini xoxlasangiz, o'sha qismni C yoki C++ dasturlash tillarida yozib, keyin shu qismni Python kodingiz orqali ishga tushirsangiz (chaqirsangiz) bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, Python juda ham ko'p, foydali hamda xilma-xil dasturlar kutubxonalarga egaligi ham juda muhimdir. O'quvchilarga ushbu dasturlashni o'rgatishdan oldin eng birinchi navbatda uning afzalliklari, qulayliklari, unda o'ziga xos bo'lgan jihatlari haqida tushuncha berish lozim. Chunki o'quvchilar o'z qiziqmay turib u dasturlashning ichiga chuqur kira olmaydi, uni o'rganishga xohish uyg'onmaydi. Shuning uchun ham ularni qiziqtirish uchun turli xil ko'rgazmali qurollar, dasturlashdagi qilingan natijalar haqida aytib o'tish, ko'rsatish joiz.

Pythonning o'ziga xosligi 1. Oddiy, o'rganishga oson, sodda sintaksisga ega, dasturlashni boshlash uchun qulay, erkin va ochiq kodlik dasturiy ta'minot. 2. Dasturni yozish davomida quyi darajadagi detallarni, misol uchun xotiraniboshqarishni hisobga olish shart emas. 3. Ko'plab platformalarda hech qanday o'zgartirishlarsiz ishlay oladi. 4. Interpretatsiya qilinadigan til. 5. Kengayishgamyoyil til. Agar dasturni biror joyini tezroq ishlashini xoxlasak shu qismni C yoki C++ dasturlash tillarida yozib keyin shu qismni python kodi orqali ishga tushirsa (chaqirsa) bo'ladi. 6. Juda ham ko'p xilma-xil kutubxonalarga ega. 7. xml/html fayllar bilan ishlash 8. http so'rovlari bilan ishlash 9. GUI (grafik interfeys) 10. Veb saytlarni yaratish. Ushbu qulayliklar, o'ziga xosliklar o'quvchilarni o'ziga jalb qila oladi. Ular bu dasturlashni qiziqib o'rgana boshlasa, computer savodxonligi yanada oshadi. Dasturlashlarni o'rgana

boshlaydi. Albatta dasturlashlarning xilma xil turlari mavjud. Ulardagi o'ziga xosliklar ham bir-biridan ajralib turadi. Shuning uchun ham o'quvchilar hozirgi kunda aynan computer sohasiga juda qiziqishmoqda. Zamon talabiga monan hozirgi kunda barcha o'quvchilar, o'qituvchi-pedagoglar komputerni juda yaxshi bilishi kerak bo'ladi.

Python dasturida ishlash tartibi quyidagicha:

1. Puskdan Python 3.7 ni topib, undan IDLEni ishga tushirish
2. Ochilgan oynaning File bo'limidan New File ni tanlash (File →New File)
3. Yangi ochilgan oynaga kodlarni kiritish va saqlash (ishchi stolida yaratilgan yangi papkaga, masalan Dasturlar nomli papkaga) (File → Save as →Ishchi stoli (Рабочи сто) →Yangi yaratilgan papka (Dasturlar) →Dastur nomi (dars_1) →Со раниТЬ (saqlash))
4. Dasturni ishga tushirish (Run →Run Module)
5. Natijani tekshirish
6. Agar dasturga biror o'zgartirish kiritilsa klaviaturdan CTRL+S klavish birikmalari yordamida qayta saqlash.
7. Har doim yangi dastur yaratilayotganda yuqoridagi tartiblar takroran bajariladi.
8. Keyingi darslarda dasturni ishga tushiramiz deyilganda yuqoridagi tartiblar tushuniladi.
9. Ma'lumotni har safar kiritayotganimizda (dastur natijasini tekshirishda) enter klavishini bosamiz.

O'quvchilarga python dasturini o'rgatish jarayonida albatta o'quvchilarning bilim darajasi ham e'tiborga olinishi kerak. Ularga komputerdan foydalanish texnikalari o'rgatilgach asta-sekinlik bilan turli xil dasturlar o'rgatila boshlanadi.

Xulosa sifatida shuni aytish mumkinki, bugungi kunda dasturlash juda ham ahamiyatli tusga kirib bormoqda. O'qituvchilar bilan bir qatorda o'quvchilarga ham keng imkoniyatlar yaratilmoqda. Ulardan talab qilinadigan narsa bu o'z ustida ishlash, computer savodxonligini oshirish, dasturlashning tilini tushunish, dasturlashni o'rgangach albatta uni tadbiq qilish kabilar talab qilinmoqda. Bu albatta juda yaxshi natijalarni ko'rsatmoqda. O'quvchilardagi dasturlashni o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqish, ishtiyoq juda ham yuqori darajada desak adashmaymiz.

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